

Monitoring Thrombosis in ECMO Oxygenators Using Computer Vision

by

Luca Palermo

Supervised by Dr. Kelly E. Michaelsen

A senior thesis submitted in partial fulfillment of
the requirements for the degree of

Bachelor of Science
With College Honors

Computer Science

University of Washington

June 2026

Presentation of work given on 5/15/26

Thesis and presentation approved by Kelly E. Michaelsen

Date 6/5/26

© 2026 Luca Palermo

ABSTRACT

Extracorporeal membrane oxygenation (ECMO) circuits oxygenate and decarboxylate venous blood as a form of life support for pulmonary and cardiac dysfunction but carry risks of thrombosis and associated patient complications. At the University of Washington Medical Center - Montlake, ECMO specialists monitor thrombosis every four hours by visually assessing the oxygenator's transparent window and maintaining hand-drawn images of the current thrombotic burden. This project seeks to determine if inter-day and inter-nurse accuracy can be improved through computer vision algorithms and a clinical interface that intake an image of an oxygenator taken on a mobile device and (1) crop the image to the oxygenator window and apply perspective correction, then (2) allow the user to tap on or circle regions of the image containing visible thrombi or fibrin to segment it from the image and predict its area to track growth over time.

An institutional review board-approved study was previously conducted to take images of oxygenators and trace boundaries of visible thrombi and fibrin strands. I created an algorithm to crop images to the oxygenator window and correct perspective from the original camera angle and created k -means based algorithms to segment thrombi and fibrin from an image given a point or freeform prompt. I fine-tuned Meta's Segment Anything 2 (SAM2) deep learning model for the same tasks to compare against my segmentation algorithms. Finally, I developed a clinical interface to integrate my algorithms. Methods were evaluated through a Bland-Altman analysis of area and diameter of segmented thrombi and fibrin, classification above or below five millimeters, and measurement of change in total thrombotic burden over longitudinal series of images.

My algorithm to crop images and apply perspective correction recovered true thrombus size within 6% ($R^2 = 0.98$). My segmentation algorithms achieved near-zero square millimeter mean bias in area (-0.18 for thrombi, 0.07 for fibrin), with 95% of thrombi within 1.93 square millimeters of ground truth and 95% of fibrin within 6.12 square millimeters. SAM2 improved fibrin's LOA to 4.85 millimeters on a limited test set. Classifying diameter above or below five millimeters yielded an F1 score of 0.70 for thrombi and 0.67 for fibrin. Change in total thrombotic burden over time had a mean PCC of 0.66, p -value of 0.09, and CCC of 0.61 against ground truth values.

These results demonstrate the feasibility of automated segmentation algorithms to non-invasively track thrombosis in real-time using images of oxygenators taken on mobile devices, and suggest a clinically viable alternative to qualitative visual assessment. The clinical interface will undergo an implementation trial this summer 2026 with preliminary results expected to be available at the American Society of Anesthesiologists' ANESTHESIOLOGY 2026 conference.

Acknowledgments

First, a huge thank you to Dr. Kelly E. Michaelsen for giving me the incredible opportunity to be a part of Gavia Labs my senior year and passing me the reigns to this project. You have been an amazing mentor and helped me discover a passion for research; thank you for taking a chance on an undergrad without any experience! I also want to thank Willis Silliman for getting the project started and for being my endless sounding board for half-baked ideas. You helped me feel right at home when I first joined the lab. Thank you to Anthony Lee for overseeing my project once I graduate, and for all of your support in prepping for the implementation trial; I know it will be in the best of hands. Thank you to Zain and Emily for the good company in lab and for always being a source of inspiration. I am so grateful to have met and worked alongside all of you! I am rooting you on with all of your future research.

I am also thankful for the efforts of Tegan Carlson, Aero Gu, and Bridget Ward in collecting images used for the dataset and annotating them, making this project possible.

Finally, thank you to my family, friends, and girlfriend, Morgan, for inspiring, encouraging, and supporting me through my research pursuits and keeping me grounded during the writing process— I can't imagine doing this without you!

Contents

1	Introduction	1
2	Background & Related Works	5
2.1	Current Methods of Thrombosis Monitoring	5
2.2	ECMO Imaging	6
2.3	Medical Image Segmentation	7
2.4	Imaging with Mobile Devices	8
3	Methods	9
3.1	Dataset	9
3.2	Prior Work	10
3.3	Cropping	10
3.4	Segmentation	12
3.4.1	Point Prompt	12
3.4.2	Freeform Prompt	15
3.5	SAM2	17
3.6	Clinical Interface	18
4	Experiments & Results	20
4.1	Experiments	20
4.1.1	Cropping	20
4.1.2	Segmentation	20
4.1.3	SAM2	22
4.1.4	Clinical Interface	23
4.2	Results	23
4.2.1	Cropping	23
4.2.2	Segmentation	23
4.2.3	SAM2	26
4.2.4	Clinical Interface	27
5	Discussion	30
5.1	Cropping	30
5.2	Segmentation	30
5.2.1	Area	30
5.2.2	Diameter	32
5.3	SAM2	32
5.4	Clinical Interface	33
5.5	Limitations	33
6	Conclusion	35

List of Figures

1	ECMO circuit diagram	1
2	Research project outline	3
3	Diagram of methods	4
4	Example dataset images	10
5	Example of k -means segmentation using point prompt	14
6	Analysis to determine k for point prompts	15
7	Analysis to determine k for freeform prompts	16
8	Screenshots of clinical interface	19
9	Results of cropping and perspective correction algorithm	24
10	Bland-Altman: k -means segmentation area	25
11	Bland-Altman: k -means segmentation diameter	26
12	Confusion matrices using ELSO threshold	27
13	Bland-Altman: SAM2 segmentation area	28
14	Total thrombotic burden change over time	29
15	Segmentation of an occluded thrombus	31
16	Example of thread-like fibrin	31

List of Tables

1	Area and IoU results for k -means algorithms	24
2	Sensitivity, specificity, and F1 score using ELSO threshold	25
3	Area and IoU results for SAM2 models	26
4	PCC, p -value, and CCC for total thrombotic growth over time	28

1 Introduction

Extracorporeal membrane oxygenation (ECMO) is a form of life support used to assume the role of a patient's lungs while experiencing or recovering from respiratory failure and facing a high risk of mortality. An ECMO circuit consists of a motor pump that intakes venous (deoxygenated) blood before it enters the heart and pumps it through an oxygenator to oxygenate and decarboxylate the blood before returning it back to the body (Figure 1). An ECMO circuit can be venovenous or venoarterial, meaning it returns the blood back to a vein, if used for pulmonary support, or back to an artery, which allows the blood to bypass the patient's heart entirely in case of cardiac dysfunction [1]. This allows the patient's heart and lungs to rest and recover while receiving ECMO support. ECMO became increasingly prevalent and important during the COVID-19 pandemic and overall usage has tripled within the last decade, with over 23,000 runs in 2024 [2].

Figure 1: Diagram of an ECMO circuit. Image from BioRender.com.

One of the most common complications in ECMO circuits is intra-device thrombosis (blood clotting), which can lead to decreased performance of oxygenation and

decarboxylation, embolic (stroke) complications, or device malfunction entirely [3]. ECMO circuits affected by thrombosis will frequently have to be exchanged, which can increase bleeding risk within the patient’s body and around the cannula sites (where the circuit attaches to the body). To attenuate intra-device thrombosis, systemic anticoagulation is used to thin the patient’s blood and reduce its ability to clot [4]. A delicate balance must be maintained to reduce clotting level within the circuit while also mitigating an increased risk of bleeding. The interior of the ECMO circuit is frequently coated with heparin, an anticoagulant, and other polymers to reduce clotting caused by foreign surface contact with blood [4]. However, the lack of a perfectly-matching biological substance causes thrombi (blood clots) to form and increases the production of fibrin strands [5], which are a large component of thrombi and contribute to similar risks. One of the most common sites (29%) of thrombi and fibrin strand formation within ECMO circuits is within the oxygenator [6]. Various methods are used to monitor thrombosis within the oxygenator and adjust the level of anticoagulant used, such as tracking the change in blood pressure as it passes through the oxygenator and the level of oxygen and carbon dioxide exchange occurring. Another method frequently used is visual assessment, which utilizes the oxygenator’s transparent window to qualitatively inspect the level of thrombosis within the device. Thrombi can be visible as small, dark, static blobs within the blood. Fibrin buildup is similar but lightly colored and sometimes seen in thread-like strands. Despite current monitoring efforts, uncontrolled bleeding due to anticoagulant imbalance requiring surgical intervention affects up to 34% of patients on ECMO [7], and 22.9% of circuits require some sort of equipment exchange due to thrombosis [3].

In the cardiothoracic intensive care unit (CTICU) at the University of Washington (UW) Medical Center - Montlake, ECMO specialists perform visual assessment to monitor thrombosis by sketching the transparent oxygenator window by hand every four hours to qualitatively report growth of thrombotic burden within the device to the attending physician. My research project seeks to replace this qualitative assessment, which is subject to ambiguity, with a quantitative measure of thrombotic burden using computer vision algorithms applied to images of oxygenators taken by specialists on CTICU-provided mobile devices (Figure 2). My work builds on an institutional review board (IRB)-approved study performed by Gavia Labs and led by Dr. Kelly E. Michaelsen in 2022-2023 which collected images of oxygenators on mobile devices from UW Montlake’s CTICU in order to determine the feasibility of developing a non-invasive imaging tool to quantitatively measure thrombosis in the future. My project contributes to this effort by using the previously collected data to (1) develop a computer vision pipeline that can reliably determine the level of thrombosis in an image of an oxygenator with prompting from an ECMO specialist and (2) the development of a web-based clinical interface for this pipeline for an implementation trial this summer. The goals of this research project were to develop algorithms robust enough that an ECMO specialist could take a photo of an oxygenator using a mobile device at an arbitrary camera angle, annotate the image on-device using prompts like

Figure 2: Research project outline: tracking thrombosis over time using images of oxygenators taken by ECMO specialists on mobile devices and applying computer vision algorithms to determine the size of thrombi and fibrin strands. Images adapted from BioRender.com.

tapping or circling a region of the image where there is a visible thrombus or fibrin strand (Figure 3), and view the calculated increase or decrease in thrombosis over time with a high level of accuracy to inform decisions on anticoagulant usage and the possibility of equipment exchange.

Figure 3: Pipeline for automatically cropping an image of an oxygenator taken on a mobile device, correcting perspective distortion caused by camera angle and segmenting selected thrombi or fibrin given prompting from an ECMO specialist.

2 Background & Related Works

2.1 Current Methods of Thrombosis Monitoring

My research project surrounds the improvement of qualitative visual assessment as a method of monitoring thrombosis within ECMO oxygenators, one of many methods used to help inform decisions on anticoagulant usage and equipment exchange. In UW Montlake’s CTICU, visual assessment is performed every four hours by the attending ECMO specialist who will visually inspect the oxygenator window to create a sketch highlighting visible thrombi and fibrin buildup. Sketches are compared over time to determine if the thrombotic burden is increasing. Visual assessment is practiced in other hospitals [8] and is outlined in the Extracorporeal Life Support Organization (ELSO)’s guidelines for ECMO management as one of the primary forms of thrombus detection [4]. ELSO specifically recommends careful observation of thrombi and fibrin within one to five millimeters and only exchanging equipment when thrombi or fibrin exceed five millimeters or are enlarging. However, these guidelines are not frequently implemented in practice and decisions on equipment exchange and anticoagulant usage are deferred to specialists’ judgment [9]. Since measurement would be cumbersome to perform by hand, sketches allow specialists to have visual references that can be compared over time to determine thrombotic burden growth.

The principal limitation to visual assessment as a method of thrombosis monitoring is its inherent subjectivity; it is difficult to unambiguously compare hand-drawn sketches, especially between specialists, and translate the comparison into a decision surrounding anticoagulant usage or equipment exchange. There are currently no studies that characterize the accuracy of visual assessment in detecting thrombosis or growth in thrombotic burden over time. Furthermore, the validity of visual assessment as a thrombosis monitoring tool is based on the assumption that surface-level thrombi and fibrin (visible through the oxygenator window) correlate with internal thrombosis. This assumption has not been rigorously verified; prior work from Evans et al. has shown a partial positive correlation ($R^2 = 0.39$) between the two metrics [10], although the regression incorporated a variety of other metrics alongside externally visible thrombi. Ongoing research from Gavia Labs under Anthony Lee, MS seeks to perform the highest resolution analysis to date of the correlation between internal and externally-visible thrombosis using micro-computed tomography (microCT), with preliminary results showing a higher degree of correlation ($R^2 = 0.80, n = 5$) [11]. Despite the absence of a statistically verified correlation between internal and surface thrombosis, visual assessment is historically widely accepted and practiced and continues to be one of the primary tools for thrombosis monitoring, justifying research into its improvement. This project will also be integrated with Lee’s ongoing study to contribute to the efforts to quantify the relationship between visible and internal thrombosis.

Other commonly used techniques to detect thrombosis include oxygenator pressure

drop, gas exchange, and patient blood testing. During ECMO, blood pressure is recorded at various locations in the circuit, specifically pre- and post-oxygenator [12]. Significant increase in pressure drop across the oxygenator can indicate a high level of thrombosis requiring equipment exchange; however, this threshold is ill-defined and varies between oxygenator models and hospital preferences [8], [12]. Monitoring gas exchange is used in some hospitals to determine the presence of thrombosis if the post-oxygenator blood has not been sufficiently oxygenated or decarboxylated [8], yet this method has not been statistically confirmed to correlate with oxygenator thrombosis [13]. Blood tests of clotting factors can indicate thrombosis within the ECMO circuit as well, such as D-dimer tests, pro-thrombin time (PT)/international normalized ratio (INR), and decreased fibrinogen levels, though poor correlation has been found between these metrics and the presence of thrombosis [13]. Despite the ongoing usage of these methods, there is a lack of statistically significant correlation with oxygenator thrombosis. While these methods can provide quantitative thresholds for decisions on equipment exchange and anticoagulant usage, they do not indicate the amount or location of thrombosis within the oxygenator. This suggests that, despite the gap in literature surrounding its efficacy, imaging oxygenators rather than relying on external variables may be a better path forward to more accurately monitor thrombosis.

2.2 ECMO Imaging

Imaging-based methods to monitor thrombosis are being explored to solve the issue of ambiguity currently faced by qualitative visual assessment of oxygenators and the lack of correlation with thrombosis that other quantitative methods face. Among the proposed solutions is the use of microCT to scan oxygenators and obtain a detailed three-dimensional visualization of thrombi and fibrin. Wang et al. [2025] explored this ex-vivo and found that volume and location data of thrombi and fibrin could be reliably imaged, segmented, and reconstructed for square and cylindrical oxygenators [14]. Lee extends this approach to circular oxygenators and specifically analyzes the correlation between thrombi and fibrin visible on the pre- and post-oxygenation surfaces to internal thrombosis to quantify how much information can truly be gleaned through visual assessment [11]. Both works demonstrate the capability and high accuracy of microCT for oxygenators, but have the limitation that the scans are performed ex-vivo after the oxygenator has already been exchanged. In-vivo CT to monitor thrombosis has been demonstrated with animal blood using phase-contrast X-rays to render images of thrombi and fibrin, although this method was not able to capture smaller thrombi [15]. The main limitations experienced by in-vivo CT are the cost of scanners, transport of critically ill patients, and exposure of blood to radiation. My project seeks to address these limitations by allowing real-time, accessible imaging with mobile device cameras instead.

Another proposed type of imaging common in the literature is optical imaging, which can analyze the composition of blood using the scattering of light. Multiple

works have demonstrated the effectiveness of optical imaging in detecting the presence of thrombi within parts of the ECMO circuit, besides the oxygenator. Namely, Morita et al. developed a micro-optical thrombus sensor that was sensitive to the presence of thrombi within the pump of an in-vitro ECMO circuit using porcine blood [16]. Although the authors note that the optical sensor can only image at very shallow depths, visual assessment relies purely on the surface of the oxygenator, making it a relevant comparison to my project’s approach. A similar method was demonstrated by Matsushashi et al. who used changes in signal intensity from an optical coherence tomography device to track the growth of thrombi area at the interface between a tube and connector in square millimeters [17]. This method demonstrates the usage of area of thrombus formation as a metric to quantify thrombosis which aligns with my project’s principal metric. The results of optical imaging techniques are scarce, have only been applied to other parts of the ECMO circuit besides oxygenators, and are limited to the surface of the oxygenator; however, they align with my approach in the shared goal of non-invasive, real-time, area-based quantification of thrombosis at a much lower cost than CT scanning.

Improved methods to image ECMO oxygenators in real-time to monitor thrombosis have been proposed but not demonstrated. Leerson et al. suggests the use of ultrasound imaging similar to the Extracorporeal Life Support Assurance (ELSA) monitor which tracks blood flow through the oxygenator. Such a method could be cost-effective, penetrate the oxygenator’s internal material, and avoid radiation exposure, but risks the oxygenator’s internal structure scattering the ultrasound signals and complicating measurement [13]. Surface-based monitoring of oxygenators using a camera and image processing algorithm has not yet been explored. My research falls directly in this gap, by seeking a quantitative solution to thrombosis monitoring that does not require specialized equipment and focuses solely on the surface of the oxygenator.

2.3 Medical Image Segmentation

Segmenting medical images is an increasingly common intersection of computer vision and medicine. Computer vision broadly encompasses the automated extraction of data from digital images, becoming increasingly frequently intertwined with the use of artificial intelligence and machine learning. Image segmentation specifically refers to the precise classification of pixels in an image comprising a target class, such as a tumor, or in this case, a thrombus. Most current research surrounding image segmentation employs deep learning (multi-layered neural networks) to achieve this goal. U-Net is a machine learning model released in 2015 specifically for biomedical image segmentation, and other models like DeepLab have also been successful at medical image applications [18]. Both models are based on a convolutional architecture, a technique of repeatedly splitting an image or feature space into patches and applying spatially local transformations to learn a task. More recent models like

Meta’s Segment Anything (SAM) are built on the novel transformer architecture and are optimized for zero-shot segmentation, meaning they can segment instances of new classes in images without being trained on any examples of that class [19]. This level of generalization is not commonly found in medical image segmentation models, frequently due to scarcity of large-scale medical imaging data. This has led to adoption of zero-shot models like MedSAM, which extends SAM for biomedical image applications [20]. However, generalizable models like MedSAM are optimized for specialized imagery like CT scans or X-rays and performance declines with natural RGB images [20]. Images of oxygenator windows, like the ones used in my project, fall in this gray area—biomedical in nature but imaged with a regular camera. There are no previous studies assessing the performance of image segmentation models, biomedical or otherwise, on images of oxygenator windows, in part due to the lack of a robust, open-source dataset for this purpose. My research uses a limited dataset of this nature collected from UW Montlake to explore the application of deep learning for the task of thrombosis detection in oxygenator images as a comparison to image segmentation algorithms developed with traditional computer vision methods. Research from Zhang et al. implements SAM for efficient use in mobile devices, suggesting a viable option for on-device, deep learning-based segmentation of oxygenator images to monitor thrombosis [21].

2.4 Imaging with Mobile Devices

The use of a mobile device for oxygenator thrombosis monitoring has not been previously explored, but ongoing research surrounds the usage of low-cost, accessible technology like mobile devices for medical applications. Multiple works specifically focus on the use of a mobile device camera for blood imaging and automated analysis, relating to some of the blood testing methods used as a thrombosis indicators. Chan et al. developed a mobile application which uses a mobile device camera and lightweight attachment to vibrate a drop of blood and track the micro-mechanical movements of an added copper particle in order to calculate PT/INR ratio [22]. Wang et al. [2016] developed HemaApp, a mobile application for blood hemoglobin concentration monitoring using the mobile device’s camera to perform a chromatic analysis on light shining through the user’s finger to screen for anemia [23]. Despite the difference in domains, both works suggest that real-time images from a mobile device camera in ambient or device-controlled lighting conditions (such as flash) can be used with computer vision-based algorithms and see near-clinical grade results. My project differs in that there does not exist a clinical control and deep learning solutions will be explored alongside traditional computer vision-based algorithms, but the similarities in methods and limitations are promising.

3 Methods

All methods were implemented in Python (v3.13) [24] using OpenCV (v4.12) [25], scikit-image (v0.25) [26], scikit-learn (v1.7) [27], and NumPy (v2.2) [28] for image processing, morphological, and mathematical operations. PyTorch (v2.11) [29] was used for model training.

3.1 Dataset

Medical students worked with ECMO specialists at UW Montlake from 2022-2023 under an IRB-approved study to take 240 images of in-use oxygenators of various shapes and models, comprising images with and without visible thrombi and fibrin buildup. 174 images were taken of square Getinge HLS Set Advanced oxygenators, 46 images were taken of circular Medtronic Nautilus oxygenators, and 48 images were taken of cylindrical Eurosets AMG PMP oxygenators. Images were taken using a mobile device with a 12 megapixel camera and f/1.6 aperture at 4K resolution, held vertically roughly one foot from the oxygenator. Most images were taken using on-device flash or with a flashlight positioned near the mobile device to simulate lighting conditions when ECMO specialists perform visual assessments. The Nautilus oxygenators had images taken from both pre- and post-oxygenation sides while the HLS oxygenators were only taken from the post-oxygenation side. Images were taken of the same oxygenators over multiple days, and some HLS oxygenators had images taken from a variety of different angles during a single imaging session. Example images of Nautilus and HLS oxygenators are shown in Figure 4.

To annotate the collected images, ECMO specialists directed medical students to regions of the oxygenator window in the image where thrombi and fibrin strands were visible, and the medical students drew boundaries around the thrombi and fibrin and labeled each annotation with its category using Computer Vision Annotation Tool (CVAT) [30]. The medical students also traced the outline of where blood is present in the image (for 145 of the images). There were 412 thrombi outlined and 635 fibrin strands outlined. There were also 36 annotations of the boundaries of plastic in some images.

These annotations were trimmed down due to various factors. All cylindrical oxygenator images and related annotations were discarded because that type of oxygenator is no longer in use in UW Montlake’s CTICU. The plastic annotations were not used in this project. Most (150) of the images of HLS oxygenators could not be used for testing the image cropping algorithm because they were already cropped before being added to the dataset, leaving 24 uncropped images of HLS oxygenators. A number of annotations were manually reviewed and discarded due to inaccuracies, preserving 157 thrombi and 317 fibrin annotations.

Figure 4: Example dataset images of a Nautilus oxygenator (left) and an HLS oxygenator (right).

3.2 Prior Work

Willis Silliman, MS and former laboratory research assistant of Gavia Labs, designed baseline algorithms for cropping the images of Nautilus and HLS oxygenators. The algorithm for Nautilus oxygenators resizes the image so that the longest side is 512 pixels long, then converts the image to grayscale, equally weighting the green and blue color channels and ignoring the red channel to isolate the borders around the blood visible through the oxygenator window (Figure 4). Canny edge detection is performed with a lower threshold of 300 and an upper threshold of 500 [31]. A random sample consensus (RANSAC) is used to fit a circle equation using 6,000 samples of three random points within the detected Canny edges [32], and the fitted circle with the smallest radius is used as the final cropping boundaries. For HLS oxygenators, a similar RANSAC method is used to fit line segments to the Canny-processed image by taking 10,000 samples of two points to fit 50 line equations. Intersections between fitted lines with positive and negative slopes are found, of which the innermost are chosen to create a rough mask around the oxygenator. The Hough transform is performed on the masked region, which similarly detects line segments [33], and the positive and negative intersections between these lines are used as candidate corner points. Hierarchical (agglomerative) clustering groups the candidate corners into four groups and the innermost candidate corner of each group is chosen as the corners of the oxygenator to crop the image. Silliman also wrote a number of helper functions for processing the images and annotations.

3.3 Cropping

My contributions began with rewriting the algorithm to crop images of square HLS oxygenators, specifically introducing a perspective transform to map every image into

a perfect square. This corrects for distortion of thrombus and fibrin area caused by the angle that the mobile device camera is held at and normalizes image dimensions. The implementation of this algorithm allows ECMO specialists to hold the mobile device themselves and more easily take a picture of the oxygenator instead of requiring a stand or tripod to image the oxygenator at an exact 90 degree angle. My algorithm starts by resizing the image so that the longest side is 1,024 pixels and converting to grayscale with default color weights. Let (H, W) represent the resized dimensions of the image. The grayscale image is normalized so its minimum value is zero and maximum value is 255 to help account for lighting differences between images. This step was found to increase the performance of Canny edge detection across HLS images. A Gaussian blur is applied with a 5×5 kernel to reduce background noise. This kernel was found to reduce sharp lines in the background so they are not picked up when detecting edges and lines in the image but the oxygenator edges remain distinct. Next, Otsu’s method is used to determine the intensity threshold t separating the foreground of the image from the background to heuristically determine thresholds for Canny edge detection rather than hard-coding values [34]. Canny edge detection is performed on the blurred image with a lower threshold of $\frac{3}{2}t$ and an upper threshold of $2t$. These thresholds were experimentally determined to find the best outline of the oxygenator given the lighting conditions of the HLS images in the dataset. Line segments are then detected in the binary Canny output using the probabilistic Hough transform (which deterministically finds instances of objects using a voting procedure) with parameters $\rho = 1$, $\theta = \frac{\pi}{180}$, a threshold of 150 votes, a minimum line length of 30 pixels, and a maximum line gap of 0. Similarly, these parameters were manually tuned so that every image of an HLS oxygenator in the dataset had at least one line segment fitted to each of the oxygenator window’s four edges. Let the line segments detected by the Hough transform be represented by set L . These filter the Canny edges to likely boundaries of the oxygenator window, and are then analyzed pairwise to detect intersections between lines with roughly opposite reciprocal slopes (within a tolerance of 25% of the magnitude of the slopes) in order to find candidate corners of the oxygenator window, described as follows for slopes m_1, m_2 :

$$c_{candidates} = \left\{ \left| m_1 - \frac{-1}{m_2} \right| \leq 0.25 \cdot \frac{-1}{m_2} \mid m_1, m_2 \in L \right\} \quad (1)$$

The 25% relative tolerance applied when considering opposite reciprocal slopes was found to be lax enough that slight imperfections in slopes of the actual edge line segments are accepted but lines detected in the background of the image that form spurious intersections with the foreground line segments are ignored. These candidate corners are grouped into four clusters using k-means clustering [35] with initial centroids $\mu_0, \mu_1, \mu_2, \mu_3$ set to the middle of the left, top, right, and bottom of the image:

$$\mu_0, \mu_1, \mu_2, \mu_3 = \left(0, \frac{H}{2} \right), \left(\frac{W}{2}, 0 \right), \left(W, \frac{H}{2} \right), \left(\frac{W}{2}, H \right) \quad (2)$$

These initial centroids match the expected orientation of the oxygenator (Figure 4, right) to aid in convergence of the k-means clustering algorithm and provide deterministic results. The mean distance between adjacent centroids of the four clusters (left and top, left and bottom, top and right, etc.) is calculated as the expected side length \bar{s} of the oxygenator window:

$$\bar{s} = \frac{1}{4} \sum_{i=0}^3 \|\mu_i - \mu_{(i+1) \bmod 4}\|_2 \quad (3)$$

This value is used to remove candidate corner points that are far from the cluster centroids or lie in between two clusters; both cases are unlikely to be the real corner of the oxygenator window. Specifically, given a cluster S_i containing a set of points \mathbf{x} , points whose closest neighboring cluster center is less than 80% of the expected side length are discarded:

$$S_i = \{\min \{\|\mathbf{x} - \mu_{i-1}\|_2, \|\mathbf{x} - \mu_{i+1}\|_2\} \geq 0.8\bar{s} \mid \mathbf{x} \in S_i\} \quad (4)$$

Finally, the innermost point of each filtered cluster is selected as the “true” corner of the oxygenator. The image is upscaled back to its original dimensions and the detected corners are mapped to a perfect square using a perspective transformation. The side lengths of the square are the minimum of 1,500 pixels or the mean distance between each adjacent pair of true corners. The transformed square image comprises the extent of the transparent oxygenator window and can then be used for segmentation.

Other methods of detecting the oxygenator window in the original image involved using the scale-invariant feature transform (SIFT) to detect keypoints in the image that could be matched to previously-computed features of an image of an oxygenator [36], but this method was not continued due to much slower processing time and inconsistent keypoint finding. Another attempted method, building off of Silliman’s original algorithm, was using RANSAC to fit a square object to sampled points, but this was not implemented due to the vastly improved efficiency of the Canny and probabilistic Hough algorithm over RANSAC.

3.4 Segmentation

3.4.1 Point Prompt

The first method I investigated to transform an input from an ECMO specialist into an image segmentation is using a point prompt. In the context of a clinical interface, this represents tapping on a pixel in an image that is within the boundaries of a visible thrombus or fibrin strand. I implemented this algorithm using traditional computer vision techniques, detailed in this section, and later compared this against a deep learning model trained for the same application (see SAM2).

To perform automatic segmentation of thrombi and fibrin with point prompts, an image patch of size 150×150 pixels is considered, centered at the seed point. This patch size was experimentally determined to optimize the computational efficiency and precision of the k-means clustering algorithm, used later in this pipeline. This patch size also limits the variation in pixel values, roughly containing the area to the thrombus or fibrin strand and immediate local context. The possibility of thrombi or fibrin extending beyond this window is possible, especially with seed points lying near the edges of the thrombus or fibrin strand. In the context of a clinical interface, such large thrombi and fibrin can be segmented using multiple point prompts. This image patch is then preprocessed in preparation for k-means clustering: the image is converted to grayscale using a weighting of 80% red values and 20% green values, discarding blue values entirely. I visually inspected the color channels and found that the blue channel only comprises the plastic on the surface of the oxygenator and lighting glare, while the red channel carries most of the blood and fibrin information and the green channel provides increased contrast between blood, thrombi, and fibrin. The evaluation detailed in [Experiments](#) was performed with a range of red to green color weights to determine the optimal ratio, with an 80% to 20% ratio yielding the best results.

Histogram equalization is then applied to the grayscale image patch, which redistributes the color values so that every color is represented by an approximately equal number of pixels. This dramatically increases the contrast of the image, making the thrombus or fibrin distinct from the background for easier segmentation (Figure 5). A 5×5 Gaussian blur is applied to reduce the effect of noise in the image such as from dust, glare, or marks on the oxygenator window. The fully pre-processed image patch then has k-means clustering applied to homogenize the pixels comprising the thrombus or fibrin and separate it from the background. For thrombi, the optimal number of clusters k was determined to be eight, and for fibrin, the optimal k was determined to be six (Figure 6). The initial centroids for k-means clustering are set randomly except for one cluster which is set to the average color value of the 4×4 pixel neighborhood surrounding the point prompt. This aids in the convergence of the k-means clustering algorithm by initializing a centroid to a value close to its expected final value, and the neighborhood average accounts for noise if the prompted pixel value is drastically different from its local context. After the image patch has been clustered into eight distinct colors for thrombi or six distinct colors for fibrin, a flood fill is applied to the original seed point with a tolerance of zero, creating a mask that contains the cluster of pixels starting at the seed point that are all the same color. This mask is a rough segmentation of the thrombus or fibrin strand that was tapped on. A morphological opening (erosion followed by dilation) and closing (dilation followed by erosion) is applied to the flooded mask with a 3×3 kernel. These convolutional operations slide across the mask, smoothing its edges and removing small holes in the mask due to noise that was not grouped in the same cluster as the seed point.

Figure 5: Example of the computer vision pipeline for segmenting a thrombus in an image with a point prompt. A 150×150 pixel image patch is considered around a seed point (left). The patch is converted to grayscale with custom weights, has histogram equalization applied, and is blurred before undergoing k-means clustering (center). The clustered image is flood filled at the seed point with the resulting mask used as the final segmentation (right).

Point prompts have additional minor complexities added to the algorithm due to the nature of a single pixel prompt on a noisy dataset and the expected behavior in a user interface. Namely, (1) there must be a result when the prompt is given, (2) it must include the point that was given as a prompt, and (3) the resulting segmentation must be contiguous. These post-processing methods are used in a minority of thrombi and fibrin annotations in the dataset when experiments were carried out. It is possible that the segmentation algorithm detailed thus far will return an empty mask because the clustered region at the given point was so small that the morphological closing removed it at the very end. In this case, we apply a flood fill on the pre-processed (unclustered) image, using a conservative tolerance of five. This selects the pixel at the seed point and neighboring pixels whose difference in color value is less than or equal to five. Another morphological opening and closing is applied to smooth the mask. If there is still no area selected, the tolerance is increased by two and this process is repeated until an area is selected. This brute force method uses heuristics of the features we extracted through grayscale and histogram equalization in the pre-processed image to approximate the segmentation. Our second similar concern is of the prompt point getting eroded by the morphological closing at the end of the algorithm, despite there still being a segmented area. In a clinical interface, this would be unexpected behavior (since the ECMO specialist is tapping on the location of a thrombus), so it is an invariant that the tapped pixel is included in the final segmentation. In the case that it is not, we find the pixel in the mask closest to the prompt point and draw a semi-ellipse to interpolate the mask from the prompt point. The endpoint of the semi-ellipse is set to the seed point and the minor radius of the ellipse is set to five, which was chosen based on the average radius of thrombi and fibrin annotated masks in the dataset. The major radius of the semi-ellipse is the distance to the closest point of the mask, to ensure it connects. The angle of the semi-ellipse is set to the direction of the closest point of the mask relative to the prompt

Figure 6: Analysis to determine the optimal number of clusters k for applying k-means clustering to a grayscale image patch with a point prompt. The k that jointly resulted in the smallest absolute mean bias for a Bland-Altman plot (segmented area minus annotated area) and highest intersection over union (IoU) score were selected separately for thrombi and fibrin.

point, calculated by the arctangent of the x and y distance. This essentially stretches the mask to include the prompt point. Finally, to address our third concern to ensure a contiguous region is selected, another flood fill is performed at the prompt point after all of the above processing. This is necessary in the case that the morphological closing eroded a thin connection between two larger regions of the mask.

Before finding success with a k-means focused approach, numerous other methods were attempted such as flood filling with a tolerance value calculated using Otsu’s method, active contour models [37], Canny edge detection, Chan-Vese segmentation [38], and the watershed algorithm [39]. These methods were not robust enough for the lack of contrast in pixel values and level of noise in the dataset and could not reliably produce a segmented mask. Implementations of these approaches did not advance far enough to be included in experiments.

3.4.2 Freeform Prompt

A freeform prompt was explored in addition to a single point prompt. For the clinical interface, this represents allowing a specialist to draw a border around a region of the image containing one or more thrombi or fibrin strands to segment the contained area. This approach was explored because of the natural, intuitive manner in which it allows annotating an image of an oxygenator and to see if the experimental results of the point prompt algorithm could be improved upon.

The core algorithm for segmentation with a freeform prompt is the same as for point prompts, without the additional post-processing complexities that were outlined. However, instead of a 150×150 pixel patch, we can simply segment the region of the image bounded by the freeform prompt. The optimal number of clusters k for

Figure 7: Analysis to determine optimal k clusters with freeform prompt segmentation. The k that jointly resulted in the smallest absolute mean bias (segmented area minus annotated area) and highest IoU were selected separately for thrombi and fibrin.

the k -means clustering step was determined to be four for thrombi segmentation and three for fibrin (Figure 7). Since this algorithm is not given a single seed point and it is not guaranteed that the center of the freeform prompt is contained within the thrombus or fibrin, we have to heuristically determine which cluster of the k -means output is the one corresponding to the area of the thrombus or fibrin. To do so, we designate the darkest cluster as the one containing the thrombus, or the lightest cluster for fibrin, and select this area as our mask before applying a morphological opening and closing. This algorithm does not have to consider seed point erosion or discontinuities in the mask because it is not given a seed point and because it is possible to include multiple thrombi or fibrin in one segmentation using a freeform prompt.

Additional variations of my k -means segmentation algorithm were explored to improve results but were not ultimately implemented. Namely, automatically determining the number of clusters k rather than keeping it constant for every image window. This step of the algorithm is critical to determining the boundaries of the thrombus or fibrin strand and is where failure cases occur when k is too high or too low for a given image. I attempted to use algorithms like G-means [40] and X-Means [41] to automatically determine the best k , but these algorithms did not perform well with this specific image data, yielding arbitrary k results. I also did a complex analysis of image metrics for the worst-performing images and best-performing images to attempt to find threshold values that could signal when k should be increased or decreased. I tracked entropy, standard deviation, inertia ratio, Calinski-Harabasz score, silhouette score, number of peaks, high gradient ratio, Laplacian variance, and local variance. None of the metrics had a statistically significant threshold between the expected value on a “bad” image or a “good” image, so these methods were not

implemented.

3.5 SAM2

I trained deep learning models to perform the same segmentation tasks described above in order to compare performance against k -means based algorithms. A deep learning model was not the principal method explored due to the limited dataset size. I chose to fine-tune Meta’s Segment Anything 2 (SAM2) model [42] for the research tasks instead of MedSAM (described in [Medical Image Segmentation](#)) due to MedSAM’s reduced performance on RGB images [20]. Four models were fine-tuned: thrombus segmentation with point prompts, thrombus segmentation with bounding box prompts, fibrin segmentation with point prompts, and fibrin segmentation with bounding box prompts.

To construct datasets for fine-tuning, I sampled two random points within the annotated mask for all thrombus and fibrin annotations in the Nautilus images, using a function described in [Experiments](#) to ensure the points are not on the very edge of the masks. The first random point is used as the center of a 150×150 pixel patch of the original image of the oxygenator window containing the thrombus or fibrin (to ensure a random offset so that the thrombi and fibrin are not always centered). The second point is used as a point prompt for that image. The maximum and minimum x and y values of the mask within the image patch are used as the bounding box prompt for that image. The annotated mask of the original image is cropped to the same boundaries as the 150×150 pixel patch. Each image patch and corresponding mask may have more than one thrombi or fibrin strand visible near dense clusters of the image, but only one thrombi or fibrin strand is prompted in each image and the outputs are filtered so that background predictions are ignored. The resulting image patches and ground truth masks are shuffled and split into 60% training, 20% validation, and 20% testing groups. The thrombus dataset contained 93 images and ground truth masks for training, 32 for validation, and 32 for testing. The fibrin dataset contained 189 images and ground truth masks for training, 64 for validation, and 64 for testing.

I used the `sam2.1-hiera-tiny` model for training to optimize computational efficiency with the consideration of eventually implementing a model in a mobile device. This version of the model is also used by MedSAM. I froze the weights of the prompt and image encoders and only fine-tuned the mask decoder. I used a combined loss function that equally weights Dice loss and binary cross-entropy loss. These loss functions correspond to the metrics used in evaluating my other algorithms with area and intersection over union (IoU), described in 4.1. Binary cross-entropy loss measures the per-pixel accuracy of the predicted segmentation, while the Dice coefficient is similar to IoU (two times the area of intersection of the predicted and ground truth masks divided by the sum of the areas). Both loss functions are standard for image segmentation tasks by optimizing for size and spatial location. I trained each model

on an A100 GPU for 50 epochs using an AdamW optimizer with a learning rate of 0.0001. The thrombi point model converged after 10 epochs with a train loss of 0.159 and validation loss of 0.230. The thrombi bounding box model converged after 20 epochs with a train loss of 0.113 and a validation loss of 0.227. The fibrin point model converged after 34 epochs with a train loss of 0.115 and a validation loss of 0.266, and the bounding box model converged after 21 epochs with a train loss of 0.131 and a validation loss of 0.259. All models achieved similar losses and had a similar level of overfitting to the training set, which is expected with such limited data.

3.6 Clinical Interface

Finally, I developed a clinical interface for implementing the developed algorithms to track oxygenator thrombosis over time. The interface stack is composed of a React Native web frontend [43] using the Expo framework [44], a Python backend with a Flask REST API [45], and a PostgreSQL database [46] using SQLAlchemy to interface with the backend [47]. The interface has a home page with a list of the current oxygenators in use, the last recorded image, and calculated thrombotic area for each oxygenator. Specialists can select an oxygenator to upload a new image, which will then automatically crop and the image and apply perspective correction. The user is then presented with the cropped image which they can tap or draw on to select regions of the image where thrombi or fibrin strands are visible. Once their finger lifts off the screen, the selected area is automatically segmented using the appropriate point or freeform algorithm (currently uses my k -means based segmentation algorithms). The image view can be zoomed and panned for ease of annotation. Undo and redo functionality are provided along with a freeform eraser to help refine any inaccurate annotations. Once finished, the overall thrombotic burden is calculated in square millimeters (using a similar method as described in 4.1.2) and saved. A chart can be viewed showing the change in overall thrombi and fibrin area over time. The oxygenator images and information displayed are available to all specialists on the floor to ensure full transparency and reduce ambiguity between specialists.

An implementation trial of the clinical interface will take place this summer 2026 in UW Montlake's CTICU. A medical student will familiarize themselves with the interface, train specialists how to use it, and intake feedback on its performance. The data collected through use of the interface will inform Lee's research surrounding correlation between internal and externally-visible thrombosis and will also facilitate in the construction of a larger dataset of thrombi and fibrin annotations for future improvement on my research.

Figure 8: Screenshots of the clinical interface. The homepage (left) shows a summary of in-use oxygenators, with the calculated thrombotic burden for each. After uploading an image to a specific oxygenator, the user can annotate the automatically cropped image by tapping or circling (shown in blue) regions of the image containing thrombi or fibrin (right). After the user lifts their finger, the blue marker disappears and the area is automatically segmented (shown with transparent white masks).

4 Experiments & Results

4.1 Experiments

4.1.1 Cropping

Successful evaluation of the cropping algorithm for HLS oxygenators involved quantifying how the perceived size of thrombi and fibrin is changed due to error in the corner detection process which affects how the perspective correction performs. I sought to test the change in area of a thrombus after the cropping algorithm is performed. Both the original and cropped image must undergo the same perspective correction into a perfect square, where the original image will have the ground truth corner points used as corners of the square and the cropped image will use detected corner points. In this way, I can quantify how the accuracy of the corner detection affects the size of the thrombi in the final image, post-perspective correction, that will be used for segmentation. For example, detecting a corner point too far inward in the oxygenator window would lead to inflated thrombus size by stretching that corner of the square.

Since the uncropped images of HLS oxygenators did not have visible thrombi, I overlaid 10 circles randomly within the oxygenator blood area of random radii from 20-50 pixels for each image. Then, I ran the algorithm to automatically crop the images to the oxygenator window and perform perspective correction and recorded the resulting area of the circles. Rather than comparing to the original area, since it is expected that the area should change due to the original camera angle that image was taken at, these values were compared to the areas of the same circles after running the perspective correction using the ground truth corners. To quantify the error in corner detection, the detected corners were plotted against the ground truth corners and the mean absolute error (MAE) was calculated. To visualize the resulting distortion of thrombi caused by this error, the distorted circle area after perspective correction with detected corners was plotted against the true circle area after perspective correction with the ground truth corners, and a linear regression was performed.

4.1.2 Segmentation

Segmentation results must be converted into physical dimensions to accurately assess performance in a clinical setting. In order to convert the pixel area to a physical dimension, the oxygenators were measured by hand, finding a diameter of 87.5 millimeters for Nautilus oxygenator windows and a side length of 88 millimeters for the HLS oxygenator windows. The original dataset includes annotations of blood area, which was used to finish the conversion: the number of pixels comprising the diameter of the blood area for Nautilus oxygenators was divided by 88, and number of pixels along along the side length of the HLS oxygenators was divided by 87.5. This yields the number of pixels per millimeter, and was calculated and stored per-image. To calculate the number of pixels per square millimeter, additional analysis was per-

formed. For circular Nautilus oxygenators, the number of pixels in the annotated blood area was divided by the number of pixels in a perfect circle of the same diameter. This ratio was multiplied by the square millimeter area of a perfect circle (using the measured diameter of 87.5 millimeters to calculate) to approximate the actual number of square millimeters of blood area. Next, the number of pixels comprising the blood area was divided by the square millimeter calculation of blood area for a ratio to convert pixels to square millimeters. This ratio was multiplied by every pixel area segmentation result to convert from pixels to square millimeters. Analysis of the HLS oxygenators was similar, using a square area instead of circle area for reference.

4.1.2.1 Area

The evaluation of the segmentation algorithms was designed to mock the usage of the clinical interface by an instructed user. To evaluate the point segmentation algorithm, I randomly sampled 10 points within the annotated mask for each thrombus and fibrin annotation in the dataset to use as trial point prompts for segmentation on the original image. Randomly selecting pixels within the entire mask area led to issues where pixels selected on the border of the mask were not actually contained within the thrombus or fibrin strand due to the dataset annotations not precisely matching the boundaries of the thrombi and fibrin. To abate this issue, I shrunk each mask by roughly 50% towards its centroid and sampled 10 random points within this concentrated area. The precise equation to shrink the contours of the mask is described as follows, where each pixel in the perimeter of the original mask M is moved toward the center with distance d based on shrinkage factor $\delta = 0.5$:

$$d = \sqrt{\frac{|M|}{\pi}} - \sqrt{\frac{\delta|M|}{\pi}} \quad (5)$$

For some annotated masks that are especially small, if the shrinkage resulted in an empty or invalid mask, δ was reduced by 0.05 and the shrinkage repeated until a valid mask was obtained.

After sampling 10 random points for each mask within a concentrated area of its annotation, the point segmentation algorithm was run using each point as a separate trial and the predicted mask was compared to the ground truth mask. IoU score was computed by treating the predicted mask A and ground truth mask B as sets of pixel coordinates and taking the magnitude of set intersection divided by the magnitude of set union:

$$IoU = \frac{|A \cap B|}{|A \cup B|} \quad (6)$$

The pixel area of each mask was converted into square millimeters using the method derived above. The area and IoU scores of the 10 trials were averaged and then used to calculate bias error (predicted area minus ground truth area) and 95% limits of agreement (LOA) for a Bland-Altman analysis. The LOA were calculated by ± 1.96

times the standard deviation of the bias.

To evaluate freeform prompts, each thrombus and fibrin annotation was also compared to segmentation results of 10 trials using random freeform masks. In order to construct the random freeform masks, the original annotated mask was dilated by a random kernel of side length from 5-50 pixels. Then, 0.5% of the area of the resulting mask was calculated and the value was used as the size of a kernel for a Gaussian blur to remove fine features and round the mask. These random masks were used as freeform input for segmentation, and the results of the 10 trials per thrombus and fibrin strand were averaged, again using mean bias of area in square millimeters and 95% LOA for a Bland-Altman analysis. IoU score was calculated for the freeform prompt results as well.

4.1.2.2 Diameter

A very similar experiment was performed to determine how accurate the k -means segmentation algorithms can determine the diameter of a thrombus or fibrin strand. Recall that ELSO recommends equipment exchange when thrombi or fibrin exceed five millimeters [4]. This guideline is not rigorously followed in the ICU [9], but is the only clinically relevant threshold that currently exists to compare my algorithms against. To evaluate diameter precision of the algorithms, I ran the same 10 trials for each thrombus and fibrin in the dataset using random point and freeform prompts and calculated the longest diameter of each predicted mask and compared it to the longest diameter of the ground truth masks. In order to find the longest diameter, first the convex hull of the mask was considered, which finds the smallest convex shape that can fit around the points of the mask. The perimeter of the convex hull was split into every possible pair of points, each considered as a diameter. The longest diameter was chosen and converted to millimeters using the pixel to millimeter conversion derived above. The calculated and annotated diameters were considered for Bland-Altman analysis using mean bias and 95% LOA. The five millimeter threshold was also used to calculate sensitivity, specificity, and F1 score for accurately detecting thrombi and fibrin above or below this threshold. The true positives, false positives, true negatives, and false negatives are also analyzed in a confusion matrix.

4.1.3 SAM2

The fine-tuned SAM2 models were evaluated by using the held-out test set of 32 thrombi and 64 fibrin images. For each test image, the test point prompt and bounding box along with the original image were input to the point prompt model and bounding box model, respectively. The resulting predicted mask had the same post-processing steps performed as outlined in [Methods](#), namely a morphological opening and closing to smooth the mask and semi-ellipse mask expansion to incorporate the seed point (for point prompt segmentation only). The post-processed predicted mask was compared to the ground truth mask in the dataset. The mean bias and 95%

LOA were calculated for Bland-Altman analysis as well as IoU score. The SAM2 models were not evaluated on diameter threshold detection because the test set did not contain enough thrombi or fibrin annotations above the threshold.

4.1.4 Clinical Interface

Current clinical practice of thrombosis monitoring involves sketching the oxygenator window at fixed intervals to monitor growth of thrombosis burden over time. To model the use of my clinical interface to perform this task, an experiment was performed to track growth over time. Five oxygenators in the dataset had series of images taken over time, which were used in this experiment. Ground truth growth over time of thrombotic burden was calculated by summing the area of all thrombus and fibrin annotations for each image in temporal order, and finding the percentage change from the last image. The predicted thrombotic burden for each image was then estimated using the freeform k -means segmentation algorithm for 10 trials. The percentage change in thrombotic burden over time for ground truth and predicted data was plotted to visualize similarity. To quantify the correlation between the two lines for each of the five series, the Pearson correlation coefficient (PCC) and p value were calculated. Another metric called the concordance correlation coefficient (CCC) was calculated as well. While the PCC assesses a linear relationship between the predicted and actual growth at each timestep, the CCC measures the agreement between the two values. CCC was calculated as follows, where ρ represents the PCC, μ represents the means of each ground truth and predicted measurement, and σ^2 represents the variances:

$$\rho_c = \frac{2\rho\sigma_{gt}\sigma_{pred}}{\sigma_{gt}^2 + \sigma_{pred}^2 + (\mu_{gt} - \mu_{pred})^2} \quad (7)$$

4.2 Results

4.2.1 Cropping

The areas of the circles post-perspective correction using the predicted corners and ground truth corners are plotted against each other in Figure 9 and yielded a linear regression fit indicating a 6% increase in circle area with an R^2 value of 0.98. The (x, y) coordinates of the predicted corners for each image were plotted against the ground truth corners in Figure 9 as well, and the MAE for pixel location was (0.1, 26.4).

4.2.2 Segmentation

4.2.2.1 Area

The predicted masks of 10 trials segmenting each thrombus and fibrin strand in the dataset were compared to the ground truth masks for a Bland-Altman analysis of area in square millimeters and IoU score. Results were calculated separately for

Figure 9: Results of cropping and perspective correction algorithm. Left: Plot of detected corners (blue) vs. true corners (red) post-perspective correction, for each of the 24 uncropped HLS oxygenator images. Shape of oxygenator window is overlaid. Right: Plot of circle area after perspective correction with detected corners vs. true perspective-corrected circle area, with a linear regression fit.

point prompt and freeform prompt segmentation. Both algorithms achieved near-zero mean bias for thrombi (-0.18 square millimeters) and fibrin (0.07 square millimeters). The best LOA were found from the freeform prompt algorithm which accurately predicted thrombus area within 1.93 square millimeters and fibrin area within 6.12 square millimeters. Using a point prompt increased this range by roughly two square millimeters. IoU score for segmentation was between 0.4-0.5 for thrombi and between 0.25-0.28 for fibrin. All area segmentation results are presented in Table 1. Bland-Altman plots for the freeform prompt algorithm, which outperformed the point prompt algorithm, are shown in Figure 10.

Method	Thrombi Bias \pm 1.96SD (mm ²)	Fibrin Bias \pm 1.96SD (mm ²)	Thrombi IoU	Fibrin IoU
Point	-0.07 \pm 3.96	-0.67 \pm 8.69	0.40 \pm 0.20	0.25 \pm 0.18
Freeform	-0.18 \pm 1.93	0.07 \pm 6.12	0.49 \pm 0.14	0.28 \pm 0.17

Table 1: Area and IoU segmentation results using k -means algorithms with point and freeform prompts. Mean bias (predicted area minus ground truth area) is shown with 95% limits of agreement for a Bland-Altman analysis along with IoU score. Best results for each column are bolded.

Figure 10: Bland-Altman plots of the predicted vs. ground truth area of thrombi (left) and fibrin (right) using my k -means algorithm with freeform prompts. Mean bias is shown with a solid blue line and the 95% limits of agreement are shown with dashed red lines.

4.2.2.2 Diameter

The diameter of every thrombus and fibrin strand in the dataset was predicted using my freeform k -means segmentation algorithm. A Bland-Altman analysis was performed showing a mean bias of -0.20 millimeters for thrombi and 95% LOA within 2.03 millimeters. For fibrin, the mean bias was 0.03 millimeters and 95% LOA within 6.24 millimeters. The Bland-Altman plots for both are shown in Figure 11. When considering ELSO’s five millimeter guideline as a threshold decision for replacing the oxygenator, thrombi diameter threshold prediction had an F1 score of 0.70 and fibrin had an F1 score of 0.67. A breakdown of sensitivity and specificity is shown in Table 2 and confusion matrices are shown in Figure 12.

Type	Sensitivity	Specificity	F1
Thrombi	0.54	1.00	0.70
Fibrin	0.66	0.96	0.67

Table 2: Sensitivity, specificity, and F1 score for determining if thrombi and fibrin are above ELSO’s five millimeter threshold for oxygenator replacement. Diameter of thrombi and fibrin was determined from predicted masks using my freeform prompt k -means algorithm.

Figure 11: Bland-Altman plots of the predicted vs. ground truth diameter of thrombi (left) and fibrin (right). Thrombi and fibrin were segmented using my k -means algorithm with freeform prompts. Mean bias is shown with a solid blue line and the 95% limits of agreement are shown with dashed red lines.

4.2.3 SAM2

The four SAM2 fine-tuned models for thrombi and fibrin with point and bounding box prompts also achieved near-zero mean bias on the test set of 32 thrombi images (0.25 square millimeters) and 64 fibrin images (-0.74 square millimeters). The LOA of thrombi models were lower (3.75-4.29 square millimeters) than my segmentation algorithms. However, fibrin area segmentation LOA were within 4.85 square millimeters, notably improved over the k -means algorithms. Using a point prompt increased the LOA range for both models. IoU score for segmentation was 0.53 for thrombi and between 0.58-0.63 for fibrin. All SAM2 segmentation results are presented in Table 3, and Bland-Altman plots of the best results (point model for thrombi, bounding box model for fibrin) are shown in Figure 13.

Method	Thrombi Bias \pm 1.96SD (mm ²)	Fibrin Bias \pm 1.96SD (mm ²)	Thrombi IoU	Fibrin IoU
Point	0.25 \pm 4.29	-0.30 \pm 7.57	0.53 \pm 0.23	0.63 \pm 0.22
Bounding box	-0.56 \pm 3.75	-0.74 \pm 4.85	0.53 \pm 0.16	0.58 \pm 0.17

Table 3: Area and IoU segmentation results using SAM2 fine-tuned models with point and bounding box prompts. Mean bias (predicted area minus ground truth area) is shown with 95% limits of agreement along with IoU score. Best results for each column are bolded.

Figure 12: Confusion matrices for predicting a thrombus or fibrin to be above ELSO’s five millimeter threshold for oxygenator replacement. Diameter was calculated using predicted masks from my freeform k -means algorithm.

4.2.4 Clinical Interface

The simulated experiment to test theoretical performance of the clinical interface was plotted as predicted vs. ground truth percentage change in total thrombotic burden over time. The five oxygenators represented in the dataset with multi-day annotations are plotted separately in Figure 14 with a blue line showing the ground truth percent change in total thrombotic burden (thrombi and fibrin) and orange line showing the mean predicted value over 10 trials with a standard deviation error band. The PCC between predicted and ground truth growth ranged from 0.30 to 0.92 (mean 0.67) with p -values from <0.001 to 0.277 (mean 0.09). The CCC values ranged from 0.29 to 0.91 (mean 0.61). Table 4 contains the full results for each oxygenator’s time series. True clinical results of the interface are forthcoming after an implementation trial is performed at UW Montlake’s CTICU this summer. An abstract was submitted to present at the American Society of Anesthesiology’s ANESTHESIOLOGY 2026 conference in October.

Figure 13: Bland-Altman plots of the predicted vs. ground truth area of thrombi (left) and fibrin (right) using SAM2 fine-tuned models. Thrombi were segmented using the point prompt model, and fibrin strands were segmented using the bounding box model. Mean bias is shown with a solid blue line and the 95% limits of agreement are shown with dashed red lines.

Series	PCC	p -value	CCC
1	0.86	0.003	0.80
2	0.92	0.001	0.91
3	0.73	<0.001	0.69
4	0.30	0.277	0.29
5	0.52	0.189	0.35
Mean	0.66 ± 0.25	0.09 ± 0.13	0.61 ± 0.28

Table 4: Correlation results of the simulated interface usage comparing predicted vs. ground truth percent change in total thrombotic burden over time. Images from five different oxygenators collected over time were segmented using my k -means algorithm with freeform prompts. The percentage change in total area of thrombi and fibrin of successive images is compared using the Pearson correlation coefficient (PCC), p -value, and concordance correlation coefficient (CCC).

Figure 14: Time series of five oxygenators percent change in total thrombotic burden (all thrombi and fibrin). Ground truth percent change is shown with solid blue line, and predicted percent change using my freeform k -means algorithm is shown in a dashed orange line with a standard deviation error band.

5 Discussion

5.1 Cropping

The results of the algorithm to automatically crop and correct perspective of oxygenator images shows a robust ability to recover the true area of thrombi and fibrin visible within the oxygenator window given the lighting conditions present in the dataset. The minor pixel offset when detecting corners only introduces a 6% inflation in perceived thrombus or fibrin size. The high R^2 value of 0.98 and strong linear regression fit indicate that this inflation can be systematically accounted for, either by adding an offset to the detected corners or by scaling down predicted area results from thrombi and fibrin segmentation. The performance of this algorithm suggests that an ECMO specialist can easily take images of oxygenators with a handheld mobile device without using a tripod or stand to ensure a perfect 90 degree angle of the camera and the oxygenator window. This underscores the accessibility of my clinical interface to function entirely on a mobile device without requiring additional equipment.

5.2 Segmentation

5.2.1 Area

The area-based segmentation results of my k -means based algorithms showed that on average, the true size of thrombi and fibrin will be predicted. This is a strong result that highlights the clinical readiness of my algorithms for its implementation trial. It was found that roughly 95% of results will be within two square millimeters of the true area for thrombi and within roughly six square millimeters for fibrin when using freeform prompts. Point prompts increased this range (indicating a decrease in accuracy) by about two square millimeters for both thrombi and fibrin. This suggests that freeform prompts should be preferred when used in a clinical setting to increase the accuracy of results for a minor amount of additional effort.

Point prompt segmentation performed worse due to the nature of having only a single pixel or a small neighborhood of pixels of information; this is not robust against the artifacts frequently visible in the images of oxygenator windows. Some thrombi and fibrin are visibly separated by plastic seams, tubing, and glare. With a single point prompt per thrombus or fibrin strand, discontinuities in its structure such as these cannot be overcome. Freeform prompts, on the other hand, can surround the entire thrombus or fibrin strand and ignore occluding artifacts by segmenting the area around them. A depiction of this phenomenon is shown in Figure 15.

Fibrin segmentation was worse for both types of prompting. This is due to the physical morphology of some fibrin strands represented in the dataset with thread-like structures that can be difficult to accurately segment (Figure 16). These are more difficult to segment because the algorithm is designed to help reduce thin lines in the

Figure 15: Example of an occluded thrombus that is difficult to segment, and the predicted masks of my k -means based algorithms as well as SAM2 fine-tuned models.

Figure 16: Example of thread-like fibrin that is difficult to accurately segment.

image, which are most often artifacts like plastic seams, by applying a Gaussian blur and morphological opening and closing on the final segmented area. The algorithm was optimized for segmenting blob-shaped thrombi and fibrin, so fibrin strands with thread-like structures see reduced performance.

The IoU scores for the algorithms were lower than expected given the favorable area estimation results, and there are a number of reasons for this. The main reason is that IoU conveys the proportion of overlapping pixels out of the unique pixels comprising both predicted and ground truth masks. However, the square millimeters represented by each pixel is less than 0.01; a predicted mask that is very accurate in physical dimensions may not be so in raw pixel count. There are additional factors contributing to low IoU scores given the algorithm’s design. With partially occluded thrombi and fibrin, even when using a freeform prompt, the portion of the thrombus or fibrin strand that is behind the occluding artifact is not included in the final segmentation; in the dataset annotations, however, these are included (Figure 15).

Another reason the algorithm does not always match the true annotation is the nature of k -means clustering. The number of clusters k is always the same, but some image patches may have more color variation and require more clusters to accurately segment them. Analysis was performed to see if the optimal k could be determined per-image (see 3.4.2), but a reliable method could not be derived.

The outliers in the Bland-Altman analysis show that the only results outside of the 95% LOA are underestimations of area. This is not a favorable indication in a clinical context, as it may be safer to systematically overestimate rather than underestimate thrombus size. The outliers were visually inspected to see that some of the annotated masks are simply too large, and others required an increased number of clusters k to accurately segment.

5.2.2 Diameter

The results of diameter estimation using my k -means based segmentation algorithm with freeform prompts had results very similar to area, with a near mean-zero bias and LOA within two to six millimeters. This tells us that not only does the predicted size align, but the morphology does as well, retaining the shape of the thrombus or fibrin strand. The performance of the algorithm at classifying thrombi and fibrin as above or below the five millimeter threshold defined by ELSO showed high F1 scores, suggesting a robustness when comparing both false positives and false negatives. The sensitivity of the algorithm for this purpose was weaker, conveying a probability of 0.54 that a thrombus above five millimeters will be accurately classified as such, and a probability of 0.66 for a fibrin strand. The interpretation of specificity scores tells us that there's a probability of 1 that a thrombus under five millimeters will be accurately classified as such, and a probability of 0.96 for fibrin strands. The algorithm is thus more robust against false positives than it is against false negatives, which naturally follows the results of the Bland-Altman analyses showing underestimation in outliers. A limitation of the algorithm's approach to diameter calculation which may be affecting results is the use of a convex hull to define the shape we are calculating the diameter of. For concave shapes such as thread-like fibrin morphologies with multiple strands, it is unclear whether the diameter of the mask surrounding all pixels that comprise the fibrin is a valuable model, or if the maximum thickness of each strand of the concave shape might be a better approximation.

5.3 SAM2

The fine-tuned SAM2 models performed similarly to my own k -means based algorithms, with worse performance on thrombi but better performance on fibrin using bounding box prompts. This highlights one of the advantages of deep learning to be able to learn complex morphological segmentation. The IoU scores for the SAM2 results were considerably higher than my k -means algorithms, reflecting the performance of the loss function. Jointly optimizing BCE loss and Dice loss is similar to IoU

by penalizing pixels that do not match the ground truth mask and considering the intersection of the masks as a proportion of their total area. The strong SAM2 results suggest that it is a viable model for this segmentation task, and with more data could outperform and replace the k -means based algorithms in the clinical interface.

5.4 Clinical Interface

The simulated measure of change in total thrombotic burden over time, matching the intended usage of the clinical interface, showed a high level of correlation between predicted and actual change. Qualitatively, observing the predicted and ground truth line charts show a high level of agreement, which suggests that a specialist observing the growth chart in the interface will make similar judgments based on its appearance as if presented with the true data. Majority of the time series had strong linear and agreement correlations above or around 0.7. Series 4 and 5, however, had weaker results. This was because Series 4 was comprised of a small number of thread-like, fibrin-only annotations that were solely in the tubing of the oxygenator window. This is a worst-case situation with a high level of occlusion and glare due to the tubing as well as inaccuracies due to the fibrin morphology. Series 5 only had 5-10 annotations of thrombi or fibrin on the last two images (while the earlier images had more), majority of which was fibrin. Since the metric used in this case is change in total thrombotic burden from the last image, a very small number of annotations between images will inflate the results. Overall, the annotations of total thrombotic burden are not necessarily similar to ones that may be observed in clinical practice—there is frequent spiking increases and decreases, sometimes near 100% of the last recorded thrombotic burden, while in practice it is expected to be a more gradual linear increase. This is mostly due to inconsistencies in the number of annotations between images within the same series.

5.5 Limitations

The biggest limitation of my results is the inability to compare against existing work, since there have not been any studies conducted to determine accuracy of visual assessment in thrombosis monitoring, to determine the utility of ELSO’s five millimeter threshold, or to train a machine learning model to perform a task of this nature.

The results I found are also likely biased due to the relatively small dataset. The cropping algorithm only had 24 images to test with under similar lighting conditions, so it is hard to generalize this performance for different hospitals with different lighting conditions. The vast majority of thrombi and fibrin annotations were within zero to three square millimeters in size, reducing the ability to draw conclusions about thrombi and fibrin strands larger than this. This also made it difficult to interpret the confusion matrices classifying thrombi and fibrin as above or below five millimeters in size, since there were very few positive samples. SAM2 showed impressive

performance at area prediction, but the test set is too small to conclude that it can reliably compete with my k -means based algorithms.

Due to the lack of existing literature surrounding thrombosis monitoring with camera imaging and how the surface of the oxygenator corresponds to internal thrombosis, it is unknown whether the metrics I computed are clinically useful. IoU may not be a clinically relevant metric to evaluate these algorithms, or diameter may be more important than area. An important note also is that all of my results measured agreement with the annotations in the dataset. There is no gold standard evaluation of oxygenator thrombosis visible at the surface, so the annotations are the only frame of reference that can be used. There are downsides to the way the data was collected, such as annotations not being completed in real time to verify if a thrombus or fibrin strand is actually present or if it might be from a shadow or glare. Also, there was not a strict enforcement of where the edges of a thrombus or fibrin strand are. Some annotations can be observed to have more lax edges around the visible area than others, which may be affecting agreement results with my algorithms.

Finally, it is difficult to generalize performance of the prototype interface before the implementation trial has commenced. The experiments I performed are useful litmus tests based on the pre-existing data, but more factors will be introduced in usage of the interface that are difficult to model. For example, the ability to undo or redo an annotation, access to a freeform eraser tool to refine annotations, and the use of a touch screen to draw annotations by hand (rather than on a computer, like how the dataset annotations were created). Following the implementation trial this summer, more data should be made available which will begin to elucidate how these factors may affect the results of my research.

6 Conclusion

This research sought to determine if the qualitative visual assessment of ECMO oxygenators in the CTICU could be replaced with a quantitative one using computer vision. More specifically, if an algorithm could be developed to accurately segment thrombi and fibrin strands in images of oxygenators, and if this algorithm could be developed into a clinical interface so that ECMO specialists could use it to track thrombosis in real-time within oxygenators in the ICU. Prior work from Gavia Labs on this topic involved collecting images of oxygenators, annotating boundaries around visible thrombi and fibrin, and developing baseline algorithms for cropping images of oxygenators to their transparent windows.

I redesigned the cropping algorithm for square HLS oxygenators to improve efficiency and implemented a perspective transform to correct for the original camera angle to avoid the need to use a stand when taking images of oxygenators. My cropping and perspective correction algorithm recovers the true size of visible thrombi and fibrin strands within 6%. I also developed k -means based segmentation algorithms with point and freeform prompts. My algorithms achieved approximately zero mean difference between predicted and ground truth thrombus and fibrin area, while 95% of thrombus segmentation results were within two square millimeters of the ground truth area and 95% of fibrin segmentation results were within six square millimeters. I evaluated diameter of predicted thrombi and fibrin segmentation masks to classify based on ELSO's five millimeter guideline for oxygenator replacement. My freeform segmentation algorithm had an F1 score of 0.70 for classifying the diameter of thrombi as above or below this threshold, and an F1 score of 0.67 for fibrin. I fine-tuned four deep learning models based on Meta's SAM2 to perform segmentation of thrombi and fibrin with point and bounding box prompts, which outperformed my segmentation algorithm for fibrin on a small test set and had better IoU across the board around 0.60. Finally, I developed a clinical interface using React Native and a Python Flask backend to allow ECMO specialists to use the algorithms and track thrombosis in real oxygenators at UW Montlake's CTICU which will be trialed this summer 2026. To simulate results of tracking growth over time, I used my segmentation algorithms to predict total thrombotic burden of time series oxygenator images and compared the change over time to the ground truth change over time. Using five oxygenator image series, my algorithms had a mean PCC of 0.66, mean p -value of 0.09, and mean CCC of 0.61.

The results of my segmentation algorithms suggest real clinical viability as an alternative to visual assessment, with quantifiable, consistent predictions of area and diameter and a strong correlation when measuring growth over time. Conclusions surrounding clinical utility of my results are limited by the lack of similar literature surrounding accuracy of visual assessment and camera imaging of oxygenator windows. The relatively small dataset used in my research is an important consideration making generalization difficult and possibly skewing results. The implementation trial

of my interface should aid in evaluating my methods and collecting additional data for improvements in algorithm development, model training, and interface design. Future work could involve training a model to perform the cropping and perspective correction task in hopes of additional robustness against lighting variation. Segmentation performance could also be improved by managing reflections and glare by taking images at multiple angles or recording video of the oxygenator window. Eventually, this research could lead to the automatic segmentation of images without any specialist input, removing the need to prompt areas of the image containing thrombi or fibrin. Related work from Gavia Labs under Anthony Lee will incorporate results from my interface's implementation trial to quantify the relationship between internal and externally visible thrombosis, underscoring the true clinical utility of my work.

References

- [1] Extracorporeal Life Support Organization, *What is ECMO?* Accessed: May 30, 2026. [Online]. Available: <https://www.else.org/extracorporeal-membrane-oxygenation.aspx>.
- [2] Extracorporeal Life Support Organization, *ELSO registry international summary*, Oct. 2025. Accessed: May 30, 2026. [Online]. Available: <https://www.else.org/registry/internationalsummaryandreports/internationalsummary.aspx>.
- [3] G. Makdisi and I.-w. Wang, “Extra corporeal membrane oxygenation (ECMO) review of a lifesaving technology,” *Journal of Thoracic Disease*, vol. 7, no. 7, 2015, ISSN: 2077-6624. [Online]. Available: <https://jtd.amegroups.org/article/view/4753>.
- [4] Extracorporeal Life Support Organization, *ELSO guidelines for cardiopulmonary extracorporeal life support*, version 1.4, Ann Arbor, MI, USA, Aug. 2017. [Online]. Available: https://www.else.org/portals/0/else%20guidelines%20general%20all%20ecls%20version%201_4.pdf.
- [5] A. J. Doyle and B. J. Hunt, “Current understanding of how extracorporeal membrane oxygenators activate haemostasis and other blood components,” *Frontiers in Medicine*, vol. Volume 5 - 2018, 2018, ISSN: 2296-858X. DOI: [10.3389/fmed.2018.00352](https://doi.org/10.3389/fmed.2018.00352). [Online]. Available: <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/medicine/articles/10.3389/fmed.2018.00352>.
- [6] S. Staessens et al., “Thrombus formation during ECMO: Insights from a detailed histological analysis of thrombus composition,” *Journal of Thrombosis and Haemostasis*, vol. 20, no. 9, pp. 2058–2069, 2026/05/24 2022. DOI: [10.1111/jth.15784](https://doi.org/10.1111/jth.15784). [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1111/jth.15784>.
- [7] S. R. Olson et al., “Thrombosis and bleeding in extracorporeal membrane oxygenation (ECMO) without anticoagulation: A systematic review,” *ASAIO Journal*, vol. 67, no. 3, 2021. [Online]. Available: https://journals.lww.com/asaiojournal/fulltext/2021/03000/thrombosis_and_bleeding_in_extracorporeal_membrane.12.aspx.
- [8] The Alfred ICU, *Haemolysis - Alfred ECMO guideline*, Dec. 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://ecmo.icu/daily-care-haemolysis>.
- [9] K. E. Michaelsen, *Interview on ELSO guidelines*, Personal communication on 5/15/2026.
- [10] C. Evans et al., “Externally visible thrombus partially predicts internal thrombus deposition in extracorporeal membrane oxygenators,” *Perfusion*, vol. 32, pp. 301–305, Nov. 2016. DOI: [10.1177/0267659116678679](https://doi.org/10.1177/0267659116678679).

- [11] A. Y. Lee, “Developing an understanding of ECMO oxygenator internal and surface clot burden using micro-computed tomography,” (Apr. 28, 2026), Abstract presented at UW Department of Anesthesiology Academic Evening 2026.
- [12] K. Lehle et al., “Efficiency in extracorporeal membrane oxygenation—cellular deposits on polymethylpentene membranes increase resistance to blood flow and reduce gas exchange capacity,” *ASAIO Journal*, vol. 54, no. 6, 2008. [Online]. Available: https://journals.lww.com/asaiojournal/fulltext/2008/11000/efficiency_in_extracorporeal_membrane.10.aspx.
- [13] A. Tulloh, S. Gregory, H. Buscher, F. Lopez, J. Leerson, and G. Rosengarten, “Detecting oxygenator thrombosis in ECMO: A review of current techniques and an exploration of future directions,” *Seminars in Thrombosis & Hemostasis*, vol. 50, no. 2, pp. 253–270, 2024. DOI: [10.1055/s-0043-1772843](https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0043-1772843).
- [14] J. S. H. Wang et al., “Development of a method for visualizing and quantifying thrombus formation in extracorporeal membrane oxygenators,” *Cellular and Molecular Bioengineering*, vol. 18, no. 2, pp. 197–209, 2025. DOI: [10.1007/s12195-025-00847-0](https://doi.org/10.1007/s12195-025-00847-0). [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12195-025-00847-0>.
- [15] A. Kaesler et al., “In-vitro visualization of thrombus growth in artificial lungs using real-time x-ray imaging: A feasibility study,” *Cardiovascular Engineering and Technology*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 318–330, 2022. DOI: [10.1007/s13239-021-00579-y](https://doi.org/10.1007/s13239-021-00579-y). [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13239-021-00579-y>.
- [16] N. Morita et al., “Real-time, non-invasive thrombus detection in an extracorporeal circuit using micro-optical thrombus sensors,” *The International journal of artificial organs*, p. 039 139 882 097 865, Dec. 2020. DOI: [10.1177/0391398820978656](https://doi.org/10.1177/0391398820978656).
- [17] Y. Matsushashi, K. Sameshima, Y. Yamamoto, M. Umezu, and K. Iwasaki, “Real-time visualization of thrombus formation at the interface between connectors and tubes in medical devices by using optical coherence tomography,” *PLOS ONE*, vol. 12, no. 12, pp. 1–13, Dec. 2017. DOI: [10.1371/journal.pone.0188729](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0188729). [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0188729>.
- [18] Y. Gao, Y. Jiang, Y. Peng, F. Yuan, X. Zhang, and J. Wang, “Medical image segmentation: A comprehensive review of deep learning-based methods,” *Tomography*, vol. 11, no. 5, 2025, ISSN: 2379-139X. DOI: [10.3390/tomography11050052](https://doi.org/10.3390/tomography11050052). [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/2379-139X/11/5/52>.
- [19] A. Kirillov et al., *Segment anything*, 2023. arXiv: [2304.02643](https://arxiv.org/abs/2304.02643) [cs.CV]. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2304.02643>.

- [20] J. Ma, Y. He, F. Li, L. Han, C. You, and B. Wang, “Segment anything in medical images,” *Nature Communications*, vol. 15, no. 1, p. 654, 2024. DOI: [10.1038/s41467-024-44824-z](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-024-44824-z). [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-024-44824-z>.
- [21] C. Zhang et al., *Faster segment anything: Towards lightweight sam for mobile applications*, Jun. 2023. DOI: [10.48550/arXiv.2306.14289](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2306.14289).
- [22] J. Chan, K. Michaelsen, J. K. Estergreen, D. E. Sabath, and S. Gollakota, “Micro-mechanical blood clot testing using smartphones,” *Nature Communications*, vol. 13, no. 1, p. 831, 2022. DOI: [10.1038/s41467-022-28499-y](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-28499-y). [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-28499-y>.
- [23] E. J. Wang, W. Li, D. Hawkins, T. Gernsheimer, C. Norby-Slycord, and S. N. Patel, “HemaApp: Noninvasive blood screening of hemoglobin using smartphone cameras,” in *Proceedings of the 2016 ACM International Joint Conference on Pervasive and Ubiquitous Computing*, ser. UbiComp '16, Heidelberg, Germany: ACM, 2016, pp. 593–604, ISBN: 978-1-4503-4461-6. DOI: [10.1145/2971648.2971653](https://doi.org/10.1145/2971648.2971653). [Online]. Available: <http://doi.acm.org/10.1145/2971648.2971653>.
- [24] Python Software Foundation, *Python*, version 3.13. [Online]. Available: <https://www.python.org>.
- [25] OpenCV team, *OpenCV*, version 4.12. [Online]. Available: <https://opencv.org>.
- [26] scikit-image team, *scikit-image*, version 0.25. [Online]. Available: <https://scikit-image.org>.
- [27] scikit-learn team, *scikit-learn*, version 1.7. [Online]. Available: <https://scikit-learn.org>.
- [28] NumPy team, *NumPy*, version 2.2. [Online]. Available: <https://numpy.org>.
- [29] The Linux Foundation, *PyTorch*, version 2.11. [Online]. Available: <https://pytorch.org>.
- [30] CVAT.ai, *Computer vision annotation tool (CVAT)*. [Online]. Available: <https://www.cvat.ai>.
- [31] J. Canny, “A computational approach to edge detection,” *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, vol. PAMI-8, no. 6, pp. 679–698, 1986. DOI: [10.1109/TPAMI.1986.4767851](https://doi.org/10.1109/TPAMI.1986.4767851).
- [32] M. A. Fischler and R. C. Bolles, “Random sample consensus: A paradigm for model fitting with applications to image analysis and automated cartography,” *Commun. ACM*, vol. 24, no. 6, pp. 381–395, Jun. 1981, ISSN: 0001-0782. DOI: [10.1145/358669.358692](https://doi.org/10.1145/358669.358692). [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/358669.358692>.

- [33] J. Matas, C. Galambos, and J. Kittler, “Robust detection of lines using the progressive probabilistic hough transform,” *Computer Vision and Image Understanding*, vol. 78, no. 1, pp. 119–137, 2000, ISSN: 1077-3142. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1006/cviu.1999.0831>. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1077314299908317>.
- [34] N. Otsu, “A threshold selection method from gray-level histograms,” *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 62–66, 1979. DOI: [10.1109/TSMC.1979.4310076](https://doi.org/10.1109/TSMC.1979.4310076).
- [35] J. A. Hartigan and M. A. Wong, “Algorithm as 136: A k-means clustering algorithm,” *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society. Series C (Applied Statistics)*, vol. 28, no. 1, pp. 100–108, 1979, ISSN: 00359254, 14679876. Accessed: May 22, 2026. [Online]. Available: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/2346830>.
- [36] D. G. Lowe, “Distinctive image features from scale-invariant keypoints,” *International Journal of Computer Vision*, vol. 60, no. 2, pp. 91–110, 2004. DOI: [10.1023/B:VISI.0000029664.99615.94](https://doi.org/10.1023/B:VISI.0000029664.99615.94). [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1023/B:VISI.0000029664.99615.94>.
- [37] M. Kass, A. Witkin, and D. Terzopoulos, “Snakes: Active contour models,” *International Journal of Computer Vision*, vol. 1, no. 4, pp. 321–331, 1988. DOI: [10.1007/BF00133570](https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00133570). [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00133570>.
- [38] R. Cohen, *The chan-veyse algorithm*, 2011. arXiv: [1107.2782](https://arxiv.org/abs/1107.2782) [cs.CV]. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1107.2782>.
- [39] H. Palus, “Color image segmentation,” in CRC Press, Oct. 2006, pp. 103–128, ISBN: 978-0-8493-9774-5. DOI: [10.1201/9781420009781.ch5](https://doi.org/10.1201/9781420009781.ch5).
- [40] Z. Zhao, S. Guo, Q. Xu, and T. Ban, “G-means: A clustering algorithm for intrusion detection,” in *Advances in Neuro-Information Processing*, M. Köppen, N. Kasabov, and G. Coghill, Eds., Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2009, pp. 563–570, ISBN: 978-3-642-02490-0.
- [41] D. Pelleg and A. Moore, “X-means: Extending k-means with efficient estimation of the number of clusters,” *Machine Learning*, p, Jan. 2002.
- [42] N. Ravi et al., *SAM 2: Segment anything in images and videos*, 2024. arXiv: [2408.00714](https://arxiv.org/abs/2408.00714) [cs.CV]. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2408.00714>.
- [43] Meta Platforms Inc., *React Native*, version 0.81. [Online]. Available: <https://reactnative.dev>.
- [44] 650 Industries Inc., *Expo*, version 54.0. [Online]. Available: <https://expo.dev>.
- [45] Pallets, *Flask*, version 3.1. [Online]. Available: <https://flask.palletsprojects.com>.

- [46] The PostgreSQL Global Development Group, *PostgreSQL*, version 18. [Online]. Available: <https://www.postgresql.org>.
- [47] SQLAlchemy, *SQLAlchemy*, version 2.0. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sqlalchemy.org>.

